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Fratelli Tutti: **A Call for Inclusive Love**

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Abstract: Inclusive love transcends all barriers, as implied in the teaching of *Fratelli Tutti*. It shatters the chains that keep us separate; it builds bridges. Love creates one great family, where all of us can feel at home. The spiritual stature of a person's life is measured by love. Love for others moves us to seek the best for their lives. Love impels us towards universal communion. It calls for growth in openness. At a time when various forms of fundamentalist intolerance are damaging relationships between individuals, groups and

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peoples, we have to be committed to a love capable of welcoming differences. Our hearts expand as we step out of ourselves and embrace others. A love capable of transcending borders is the basis of social friendship, to be extended to all, especially to migrants. Many migrants are seeking opportunities for themselves and their families. Like the Samaritan who cared for the wounded man, even spending his own money and time, Jesus asks us to be available to those in need of our help, a sign of real solidarity, which means thinking and acting in terms of the needs of the global community. Forgiveness and reconciliation are central to inclusive love, which can overcome the challenges of racism and fragmentation, aggressive nationalism, uncaring globalism, local narcissism, limitless consumption, empty individualism, and cultural colonization.

Keywords: Crusades, Communion, Fanaticism, Ecstasis, Fundamentalism, Compassion, Integration

Introduction

Fraternity and social friendship are the ways Pope Francis indicates to build a better, more just and peaceful world, with the contribution of all: people and institutions. What are the tangible ways to advance for those who wish to build a more just and fraternal world in their ordinary relationships, in social life, politics and institutions? This is mainly the question that “*Fratelli Tutti*” (Abbreviated as FT) is intended to answer: the Pope describes it as a “Social Encyclical,” which borrows the title of the “Admonitions” of Saint Francis of Assisi, who used these words to address his brothers and sisters and proposed to them a way of life marked by the teachings of the Gospel. The Encyclical aims to promote a universal aspiration toward fraternity and social friendship. In the background of the Encyclical is the Covid-19 pandemic which, Francis reveals, unexpectedly erupted as he was writing this letter. But the global health emergency has demonstrated that no one can face life in isolation and that the

time has truly come to dream, then, as a single human family in which we are ‘brothers and sisters all.’

The present article tries to explain the Social Encyclical as a call to inclusive love. The article is mainly divided into two parts: (1) Positive Traits of Inclusive Love and (2) Challenges to Inclusive Love.

1. Positive Traits of Inclusive Love

a. Inclusive Love Promotes Fraternity and Social Friendship

St Francis of Assisi, the saint of fraternal love, simplicity and joy, prompted Pope Francis to devote this new Encyclical to fraternity and social friendship. Francis of Assisi sowed seeds of peace and walked alongside the poor, the abandoned, the infirm and the outcast, the least of his brothers and sisters.

This saint of fraternal love, simplicity and joy, who inspired me to write the Encyclical *Laudato Si'*, prompts me once more to devote this new Encyclical to fraternity and social friendship. Francis felt himself a brother to the sun, the sea and the wind, yet he knew that he was even closer to those of his own flesh. Wherever he went, he sowed seeds of peace and walked alongside the poor, the abandoned, the infirm and the outcast, the least of his brothers and sisters. (FT 2)

Inclusive Love Transcends Barriers: *Fratelli Tutti* calls for a love that transcends the barriers of geography and distance, and declares blessed all those who love their brother “as much when he is far away from him as when he is with him.”

Fratelli Tutti, With these words, Saint Francis of Assisi addressed his brothers and sisters and proposed to them a way of life marked by the flavour of the Gospel. Of the counsels Francis offered, I would like to select the one in which he calls for a love that transcends the barriers of geography and distance, and declares blessed all those

who love their brother “as much when he is far away from him as when he is with him”. In his simple and direct way, Saint Francis expressed the essence of a fraternal openness that allows us to acknowledge, appreciate and love each person, regardless of physical proximity, regardless of where he or she was born or lives. (FT 1)

Inclusive Love Builds Bridges: Love does not care if a brother or sister in need comes from one place or another. For love shatters the chains that keep us separate; in their place, it builds bridges. Love creates one great family, where all of us can feel at home... Love exudes compassion and dignity.

Yet this call to love could be misunderstood. Saint Paul, recognizing the temptation of the earliest Christian communities to form closed and isolated groups, urged his disciples to abound in love “for one another and for all” (1 Thess 3:12). In the Johannine community, fellow Christians were to be welcomed, “even though they are strangers to you” (3 Jn 5). In this context, we can better understand the significance of the parable of the Good Samaritan: love does not care if a brother or sister in need comes from one place or another. For “love shatters the chains that keep us isolated and separate; in their place, it builds bridges. Love enables us to create one great family, where all of us can feel at home... Love exudes compassion and dignity. (FT 62)

The parable clearly speaks to us of an essential and often forgotten aspect of our common humanity: fulfilment in love. We cannot allow anyone to go through life as an outcast. Instead, we should feel indignant and challenged to emerge from our comfortable isolation. (FT 68)

Inclusive Love Embraces All: There is an episode in the life of Saint Francis that shows his openness of heart, which went beyond boundaries. It was his visit to Sultan Malik-el-Kamil, in Egypt, which entailed considerable hardship for St Francis. That journey demonstrated the breadth and grandeur of his love, which sought to embrace everyone. Some eight hundred years ago Saint

Francis urged that all forms of hostility be avoided and that a humble and fraternal “subjection” be shown to those who did not share his faith.

There is an episode in the life of Saint Francis that shows his openness of heart, which knew no bounds and transcended differences of origin, nationality, colour or religion. It was his visit to Sultan Malik-el-Kamil, in Egypt, which entailed considerable hardship, given Francis’ poverty, his scarce resources, the great distances to be travelled and their differences of language, culture and religion. That journey, undertaken at the time of the Crusades, further demonstrated the breadth and grandeur of his love, which sought to embrace everyone. Francis’ fidelity to his Lord was commensurate with his love for his brothers and sisters. Unconcerned for the hardships and dangers involved, Francis went to meet the Sultan with the same attitude that he instilled in his disciples: if they found themselves “among the Saracens and other nonbelievers”, without renouncing their own identity they were not to “engage in arguments or disputes, but to be subject to every human creature for God’s sake”. In the context of the times, this was an extraordinary recommendation. We are impressed that some eight hundred years ago Saint Francis urged that all forms of hostility or conflict be avoided and that a humble and fraternal “subjection” be shown to those who did not share his faith. (FT 3)

Inclusive Love Fosters Harmony and Peace: St Francis of Assisi simply spread the love of God. In this way, he became a father to all and inspired the vision of a fraternal society. In the world of that time, cities were a theatre of brutal wars between powerful families, even as poverty was spreading through the countryside. Yet there Francis was able to

welcome true peace into his heart and sought to live in harmony with all. (FT 4)

Inclusive Love as Divine: Issues of human fraternity have always been a concern of mine. In this case, I have felt particularly encouraged by the Grand Imam Ahmad Al-Tayyeb, with whom I met in Abu Dhabi, where we declared that “God has created all human beings equal in rights, duties and dignity, and has called them to live together as brothers and sisters”. This was a reflection born of dialogue and common commitment. (FT 5)

Inclusive Love as Fraternal: The following pages consider the universal scope of fraternal love, its openness to every human. In the face of present-day attempts to eliminate or ignore others, we may prove capable of responding with a new vision of fraternity and social friendship. The encyclical is an invitation to dialogue among all people of good will. (FT 6)

Inclusive Love as the Measurement of Spiritual Stature: The spiritual stature of a person’s life is measured by love. All of us need to recognize that love takes first place: love must never be put at risk, and the greatest danger lies in failing to love. (FT 92)

Inclusive Love Seeks the Best for Others: Love, then, is more than just a series of benevolent actions. Our love for others moves us to seek the best for their lives. (FT 94)

Inclusive Love Calls for Universal Openness: Love impels us towards universal communion. It calls for growth in openness and the ability to accept others as part of a continuing adventure that makes every periphery converge in a greater sense of mutual belonging. “Love also impels us towards universal communion. No one can mature or find fulfilment by withdrawing from others. By its very nature, love calls for growth in openness and the ability to accept others as part of a continuing adventure that makes every periphery converge in a greater sense of mutual belonging. As Jesus told us: “You are all brothers” (Mt 23:8).” (FT 95)

Inclusive Love as Foundation of Virtues: Without charity, we may perhaps possess only apparent virtues, incapable of sustaining life in common. The other virtues, without charity, do

not fulfil the commandments the way God wants them to be fulfilled. (FT 91)

Inclusive Love as Expression of Political Charity: Political charity is expressed in a spirit of openness. Government leaders should be the first to make sacrifices that foster encounter and to seek convergence on some issues. They should be ready to listen to other points of view. Through sacrifice and patience, they can help to create a beautiful polyhedral reality in which everyone has a place. It may seem utopian, yet we cannot renounce this lofty aim. (FT 190)

Inclusive Love as Welcoming Differences: At a time when various forms of fundamentalist intolerance are damaging relationships between individuals, groups and peoples, let us be committed to living and teaching the value of respect for others, a love capable of welcoming differences. Even as forms of fanaticism, closedmindedness and social and cultural fragmentation proliferate, a good politician will insist that different voices be heard. Disagreements may well give rise to conflicts, but uniformity leads to cultural decay. (FT 191)

Inclusive Love as Embracing Foreigner: In the parable of the Good Samaritan, we find a reason why our hearts should expand to embrace the foreigner. It derives from the enduring memory of the Jewish people in Egypt: “You shall not wrong or oppress a stranger, for you were strangers in the land of Egypt” (Ex 22:21). The call to fraternal love echoes throughout the New Testament: “For the whole law is summed up in a single commandment, ‘You shall love your neighbour as yourself’” (Gal 5:14). (FT 61)

b. Inclusive Love as Welcoming Migrants

Move to Stop Influx of Migrants: Certain populist political regimes maintain that an influx of migrants is to be prevented at all costs. Arguments are also made for the propriety of limiting aid to poor countries, so that they can hit rock bottom

and find themselves forced to take austerity measures. One fails to realize that behind such statements, great numbers of lives are at stake. Many migrants have fled from war. Others “are seeking opportunities for themselves and their families. They dream of a better future. (FT 37)

Response to Migrants: Unnecessary migration ought to be avoided; this entails creating in countries of origin the conditions needed for a dignified life. Yet until substantial progress is made in achieving this goal, we are obliged to respect the right of all individuals to find a place that meets their basic needs. Our response to the arrival of migrants can be summarized by four words: welcome, protect, promote and integrate. (FT 129)

Dignity of the Migrants: Migrants possess the same intrinsic dignity as any person. The inalienable dignity of each human person regardless of origin, race or religion, and the supreme law of fraternal love. (FT 39)

Protect Citizens and Help Migrants: Migrations will play a pivotal role in the future of our world. Europe has to find the right balance between its twofold moral responsibility to protect the rights of its citizens and to assure assistance and acceptance to migrants.

Migrations, more than ever before, will play a pivotal role in the future of our world”. At present, however, migration is affected by the “loss of that sense of responsibility for our brothers and sisters on which every civil society is based”.^[43] Europe, for example, seriously risks taking this path. Nonetheless, “aided by its great cultural and religious heritage, it has the means to defend the centrality of the human person and to find the right balance between its twofold moral responsibility to protect the rights of its citizens and to assure assistance and acceptance to migrants”. (FT 40)

Fear of Migrants: Some people are fearful with regard to migrants. We need to move beyond those primal reactions because “there is a problem when doubts and fears condition our way of thinking and acting to the point of making us intolerant,

racist. Fear deprives us of the desire and the ability to encounter the other.” (FT 41)

c. Inclusive Love as Helping the Needy

Samaritan Helped with Money and Time: The Samaritan stopped, approached the man and cared for him personally, even spending his own money to provide for his needs. He also gave him his time. Certainly, he had his own plans for that day. Yet he was able to put all that aside in order to care for someone in need. He saw him as deserving of his time and attention. (FT 63)

Ignoring the Needy: Let us admit that, for all the progress we have made, we are still “illiterate” when it comes to caring for and supporting the most frail and vulnerable members of our societies. We have become accustomed to looking the other way, ignoring situations until they affect us directly. (FT 64)

Imitate the Good Samaritan: The parable presents the basic decision we need to make in order to rebuild our wounded world, to imitate the Good Samaritan. Any other decision would make us either one of the robbers or one of those who walked by without showing compassion for the sufferings of the man on the roadside.

The parable eloquently presents the basic decision we need to make in order to rebuild our wounded world. In the face of so much pain and suffering, our only course is to imitate the Good Samaritan. Any other decision would make us either one of the robbers or one of those who walked by without showing compassion for the sufferings of the man on the roadside. The parable shows us how a community can be rebuilt by men and women who identify with the vulnerability of others, who reject the creation of a society of exclusion, and act instead as neighbours, lifting up and rehabilitating the fallen for the sake of the common good. At the same time, it warns us

about the attitude of those who think only of themselves and fail to shoulder the inevitable responsibilities of life as it is. (FT 67)

Becoming Neighbours to All: Jesus told the parable of the Good Samaritan in answer to the question: Who is my neighbour? The word “neighbour”, in the society of Jesus’ time, usually meant those nearest us. For some Jews of that time, Samaritans were looked down upon, considered impure and were not among those to be helped. Jesus, himself a Jew, completely transforms this approach. He asks us not to decide who is close enough to be our neighbour, but rather that we ourselves become neighbours to all. (FT 80)

Help the Needy: Jesus asks us to be present to those in need of help, regardless of whether or not they belong to our social group. (FT 81)

Gift of Self to Others: Human beings cannot live, develop and find fulfilment except in the sincere gift of self to others. They also fully know themselves only in an encounter with other persons. Life exists where there is bonding, communion, and fraternity. (FT 87)

d. Inclusive Love as Moving Beyond Ourselves

In the depths of every heart, love creates bonds and expands existence. Lover ‘goes outside’ the self to find a fuller existence in another. For this reason, human always has to take up the challenge of moving beyond oneself.

In the depths of every heart, love creates bonds and expands existence, for it draws people out of themselves and towards others.[65] Since we were made for love, in each one of us “a law of *ekstasis*” seems to operate: “the lover ‘goes outside’ the self to find a fuller existence in another”.[66] For this reason, “man always has to take up the challenge of moving beyond himself”. (FT 88)

Closed Groups as Selfish: We find that our hearts expand as we step out of ourselves and embrace others. Closed groups that

define themselves in opposition to others tend to be expressions of selfishness. (FT 89)

Unity and Common Destiny of All: This need to transcend our own limitations also applies to different regions and countries. The ever-increasing number of communications in today's world makes us powerfully aware of the unity and common destiny of all. (FT 96)

Universal Aspiration to Fraternity: In this our time, by acknowledging the dignity of each human person, we can contribute to the rebirth of a universal aspiration to fraternity. (FT 8)

e. Inclusive Love Moves Towards Integration

For decades, it seemed that the world had learned a lesson from its many wars and disasters, and was slowly moving towards various forms of integration. For example, there was the dream of a united Europe, capable of acknowledging its shared roots and rejoicing in its rich diversity.

For decades, it seemed that the world had learned a lesson from its many wars and disasters, and was slowly moving towards various forms of integration. For example, there was the dream of a united Europe, capable of acknowledging its shared roots and rejoicing in its rich diversity. We think of “the firm conviction of the founders of the European Union, who envisioned a future based on the capacity to work together in bridging divisions and in fostering peace and fellowship between all the peoples of this continent”.[7] There was also a growing desire for integration in Latin America, and several steps were taken in this direction. In some countries and regions, attempts at reconciliation and rapprochement proved fruitful, while others showed great promise. (FT 10)

f. Inclusive Love Transcends Borders

A love capable of transcending borders is the basis of “social friendship”, which makes true universal openness possible. Those who look down on their own people tend to create within society categories of first and second class people.

A love capable of transcending borders is the basis of what in every city and country can be called “social friendship”. Genuine social friendship within a society makes true universal openness possible. This is a far cry from the false universalism of those who constantly travel abroad because they cannot tolerate or love their own people. Those who look down on their own people tend to create within society categories of first and second class, people of greater or lesser dignity, people enjoying greater or fewer rights. In this way, they deny that there is room for everybody. (FT 99)

Good Samaritan as a Foreigner: The parable of the Good Samaritan has still much to say to us. He was simply a foreigner without a place in society. He was able to interrupt his journey, change his plans, and unexpectedly come to the aid of an injured person who needed his help. (FT 101)

g. Inclusive Love as Solidarity

Solidarity Calls for Commitment: Solidarity calls for commitment on the part of those responsible for education and formation. (FT 114)

Solidarity Expressed in Service: Solidarity finds concrete expression in service, which means caring for vulnerability, for the vulnerable members of our families, our society, our people. (FT 115)

Meaning of Solidarity: Solidarity means thinking and acting in terms of community. It means that the lives of all are prior to the appropriation of goods by a few, combatting the structural causes of poverty, inequality, and unemployment.

The needy generally “practise the special solidarity that exists among those who are poor and suffering, and which

our civilization seems to have forgotten or would prefer in fact to forget. Solidarity is a word that is not always well received; in certain situations, it has become a dirty word, a word that dare not be said. Solidarity means much more than engaging in sporadic acts of generosity. It means thinking and acting in terms of community. It means that the lives of all are prior to the appropriation of goods by a few. It also means combatting the structural causes of poverty, inequality, the lack of work, land and housing, the denial of social and labour rights. It means confronting the destructive effects of the empire of money... Solidarity, understood in its most profound meaning, is a way of making history, and this is what popular movements are doing". (FT 116)

h. Inclusive Love as Local and Universal

Glocalization: An innate tension exists between globalization and localization. We need to pay attention to the global so as to avoid narrowness. Yet we also need to look to the local, which keeps our feet on the ground. Together, the two prevent us from falling into one of two extremes.

It should be kept in mind that “an innate tension exists between globalization and localization. We need to pay attention to the global so as to avoid narrowness and banality. Yet we also need to look to the local, which keeps our feet on the ground. Together, the two prevent us from falling into one of two extremes. In the first, people get caught up in an abstract, globalized universe... In the other, they turn into a museum of local folklore, a world apart, doomed to doing the same things over and over, incapable of being challenged by novelty or appreciating the beauty which God bestows beyond their borders”.[124] We need to have a global

outlook to save ourselves from petty provincialism. When our house stops being a home and starts to become an enclosure, a cell, then the global comes to our rescue, like a “final cause” that draws us towards our fulfilment. At the same time, though, the local has to be eagerly embraced, for it possesses something that the global does not: it is capable of being a leaven, of bringing enrichment, of sparking mechanisms of subsidiarity. Universal fraternity and social friendship are thus two inseparable and equally vital poles in every society. To separate them would be to disfigure each and to create a dangerous polarization. (FT 142)

i. Inclusive Love Promotes Healthy Openness

A healthy openness never threatens one’s own identity. A living culture does not import a mere carbon copy of those new elements, but integrates them in its own unique way. The result is a new synthesis that is ultimately beneficial to all. (FT 148)

Global Society as Universal Communion: Global society is not the sum total of different countries, but rather the communion that exists among them. The mutual sense of belonging is prior to the emergence of individual groups, which are part of the fabric of universal communion. All individuals know that they are part of the greater human family, without which they will not be able to understand themselves fully. (FT 149)

Self-fulfilment Requires Others: No one people, culture or individual can achieve everything on its own: to attain fulfilment in life we need others. An awareness of our own limitations and incompleteness becomes the key to envisaging and pursuing a common project. (FT 150)

j. Inclusive Love Integrates and Unites

We have to work strenuously to spread the culture of tolerance and of living together in peace. When a specific policy sows hatred towards other nations in the name of its own country’s

welfare, there is need to react in time and immediately to correct the course.

In this regard, Grand Imam Ahmad Al-Tayyeb and I have called upon “the architects of international policy and world economy to work strenuously to spread the culture of tolerance and of living together in peace; to intervene at the earliest opportunity to stop the shedding of innocent blood”.[189] When a specific policy sows hatred and fear towards other nations in the name of its own country’s welfare, there is need to be concerned, to react in time and immediately to correct the course. (FT 192)

k. Inclusive Love Promotes Forgiveness and Reconciliation

There are those who prefer not to talk of reconciliation, for they think that conflict, violence and breakdown are part of the normal functioning of a society. Others think that promoting forgiveness means yielding ground and influence to others. For this reason, they feel it is better to keep things as they are. Still others believe that reconciliation is a sign of weakness.

There are those who prefer not to talk of reconciliation, for they think that conflict, violence and breakdown are part of the normal functioning of a society. In any human group there are always going to be more or less subtle power struggles between different parties. Others think that promoting forgiveness means yielding ground and influence to others. For this reason, they feel it is better to keep things as they are, maintaining a balance of power between differing groups. Still others believe that reconciliation is a sign of weakness; incapable of truly serious dialogue, they choose to avoid problems by ignoring injustices. Unable to deal with problems, they opt for an apparent peace. (FT 236)

Forgiveness and Reconciliation as Inter-religious Themes: Forgiveness and reconciliation are central themes in Christianity and in other religions. Yet there is a risk that an inadequate understanding of these profound convictions can lead to fatalism, apathy and injustice, or even intolerance and violence. (FT 237)

2. Some Challenges to Inclusive Love

a. Racism and Fragmentation

There is an aspect of universal openness in love that is existential. Every brother or sister in need, when abandoned or ignored by the society in which I live, becomes an existential foreigner, even though born in the same country. Racism is a virus that quickly mutates and goes into hiding, and lurks in waiting. (FT 97)

b. Pandemic Fragmentation

The Covid-19 pandemic has unexpectedly erupted, exposing our false securities. Aside from the different ways that various countries responded to the crisis, we witnessed a fragmentation that made it more difficult to resolve problems that affect us all. (FT 7)

c. Aggressive Nationalism

However, our own days, show signs of a certain regression. Past conflicts are breaking out anew, while instances of an extremist, resentful and aggressive nationalism are on the rise. In some countries, a concept of national unity influenced by various ideologies is creating new forms of selfishness and a loss of the social sense. These things remind us that it is not possible to settle for what was achieved in the past and complacently enjoy it, disregarding the fact that many of our brothers and sisters still endure situations that cry out for our attention.

Our own days, however, seem to be showing signs of a certain regression. Ancient conflicts thought long buried are breaking out anew, while instances of a myopic, extremist, resentful and aggressive nationalism are on the

rise. In some countries, a concept of popular and national unity influenced by various ideologies is creating new forms of selfishness and a loss of the social sense under the guise of defending national interests. Once more we are being reminded that “each new generation must take up the struggles and attainments of past generations, while setting its sights even higher. This is the path. Goodness, together with love, justice and solidarity, are not achieved once and for all; they have to be realized each day. It is not possible to settle for what was achieved in the past and complacently enjoy it, as if we could somehow disregard the fact that many of our brothers and sisters still endure situations that cry out for our attention”. (FT 11)

d. Uncaring Globalism

“Opening up to the world” is an expression co-opted by the economic and financial sector and is now used exclusively of openness to foreign interests or to the freedom of economic powers to invest without obstacles. We are in a world that promotes individual interests and weakens the communitarian dimension of life. The advance of this kind of globalism strengthens the identity of the more powerful, who can protect themselves, but it tends to diminish the identity of the weaker and poorer regions, making them more vulnerable and dependent. (FT 12)

e. Local Narcissism

Local narcissism is born of a certain insecurity and fear of the other that leads to rejection and the desire to erect walls for self-defence. Yet it is impossible to be “local” in a healthy way without being sincerely open to the universal.

There is a kind of “local” narcissism unrelated to a healthy love of one’s own people and culture. It is born of a certain insecurity and fear of the other that leads to rejection and the desire to erect walls for self-

defence. Yet it is impossible to be “local” in a healthy way without being sincerely open to the universal, without feeling challenged by what is happening in other places, without openness to enrichment by other cultures, and without solidarity and concern for the tragedies affecting other peoples. A “local narcissism” instead frets over a limited number of ideas, customs and forms of security; incapable of admiring the vast potential and beauty offered by the larger world, it lacks an authentic and generous spirit of solidarity. Life on the local level thus becomes less and less welcoming, people less open to complementarity. Its possibilities for development narrow; it grows weary and infirm. A healthy culture, on the other hand, is open and welcoming by its very nature; indeed, “a culture without universal values is not truly a culture”. (FT 146)

f. Limitless Consumption and Empty Individualism

As the document notes, there is a growing loss of the sense of history, a kind of “deconstructionism,” which is making headway in today’s culture. The one thing it leaves in its wake is the drive to limitless consumption and empty individualism. (FT 13)

g. Cultural Colonization

These are the new forms of cultural colonization. The peoples that abandon their tradition allow others to rob their very soul, end up losing not only their spiritual identity but also their moral consistency and, in the end, their intellectual, economic and political independence.

These are the new forms of cultural colonization. Let us not forget that “peoples that abandon their tradition and, either from a craze to mimic others or to foment violence, or from unpardonable negligence or apathy, allow others to rob their very soul, end up losing not only their spiritual identity but also their moral consistency and, in the end, their intellectual, economic

and political independence”. [11] One effective way to weaken historical consciousness, critical thinking, the struggle for justice and the processes of integration is to empty great words of their meaning or to manipulate them. Nowadays, what do certain words like democracy, freedom, justice or unity really mean? They have been bent and shaped to serve as tools for domination, as meaningless tags that can be used to justify any action. (FT 14)

Conclusion

Fratelli Tutti calls for a love that transcends the barriers of geography and distance. Love shatters the chains that keep us separate; it builds bridges. Love creates one great family, where all of us can feel at home. God has created all human beings equal in rights, duties and dignity, and has called them to live together as brothers and sisters. In the face of present-day attempts to eliminate others, we may prove capable of responding with a new vision of fraternity and social friendship. The spiritual stature of a person’s life is measured by love. The greatest danger lies in failing to love. Love for others moves us to seek the best for their lives. Love impels us towards universal communion. It calls for growth in openness. Without charity, we may perhaps possess only apparent virtues, incapable of sustaining life in common.

At a time when various forms of fundamentalist intolerance are damaging relationships between individuals, groups and peoples, we have to be committed to living and teaching the value of respect for others, a love capable of welcoming differences. Disagreements may well give rise to conflicts, but uniformity leads to cultural decay. We find that our hearts expand as we step out of ourselves and embrace others. A love capable of transcending borders is the basis of “social friendship”, which makes true universal openness possible.

Many migrants have fled from war. Others “are seeking opportunities for themselves and their families. The Samaritan stopped, approached the man and cared for him personally, even spending his own money and time. Jesus asks us to be present to those in need of our help, a sign of real solidarity. Solidarity means thinking and acting in terms of the global community. We need to pay attention to the global so as to avoid narrowness. Yet we also need to look to the local, which keeps our feet on the ground. Forgiveness and reconciliation are central to inclusive love. Some of the challenges to inclusive love are racism and fragmentation, aggressive nationalism, uncaring globalism, local narcissism, limitless consumption, empty individualism, and cultural colonization.

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